

Let the World Enter Into the Classrooms : A Twenty-first Century Imperative on Global Education

Gautam Bandyopadhyay

R.K.Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math

ABSTRACT : This paper deals with the tensions created by Globalization in cultural spheres and the way that strives to remove them through Global Education. The Delors Commission Report (1996), 'Learning the Treasure within' has emphasized the global concern for social crises compounded by moral crises and value crises all over the world. It represents a prevailing tensions. In order to respond to this situation appropriately and effectively, education has an important role to perform today with adequate knowledge, positive attitude and suitable approach. If it is arranged properly, that would successfully minimize and eventually eliminate some rampant social and moral evils and provide workable solutions to some serious issues related to education, culture, ecology, social health etc.

Keywords : Globalization, social ethos, global dimension, curriculum, value judgement.

Introduction

Albert Camus, the famous French existentialist, once quoted "when the imagination sleeps, words are emptied of their meaning". Indeed. A life having a very little imagination is not a life worth living. Sheer imagination is more important and powerful than mere knowledge. Hence, creation of imagination, creation of ideas are necessary for bringing any change. They affect our behaviour, outlook, our philosophy of life and ultimately our world view. Earth cannot be changed for the better unless the

consciousness of individual is changed first. One such set of ideas being promoted recently in educational circles is Global Education. Exponents of Global Education often analyse it by using a variety of other names: multicultural education, peace education, cultural studies, human rights education, international studies, futurism etc. The thought that we are the fortunate residents of a global village has broadened our mind's sky. Hopefully, the serenity, the sustainable, ethical and moral development of a so-called 'village' will encircle

our global mindset. But the concept of global village is still an evolutionary imperative.

The question is that what kind of global village we are going to have. Is it based upon terrorism, exploitation, hatred, negativism, disease like HIV? Of course not. Why do we feel then that the world is nothing but a waste land which is absolutely filled with sciolism? This is the question with which we are confronting.

The World is in severe affliction named cultural globalization

The term 'Globalization' is economy-oriented that simply means 'open air', glasnost, without any concrete primordial philosophy. West wind imbibes the east ; the east will absorb the west. The world will be a place for cultural hybridity. The picture is very alluring. But a neo-cultural imperialism is being manifested so that many people around the world argue that unless we take serious steps to strengthen traditional wisdom and indigenous culture, protect the environment, maintain the value-judgment and human rights perspectives, the overwhelming forces of globalization can, in just a few decades, wipe out our cultural and ecological diversity. Globalization poses such a serious threat that it could even lead to vanishing of such cultures as are not firmly rooted in their own soil. As a result, the seeds of demoralisation and devaluation might have taken place in the land of indecisions, the resting place for all kinds of evils. "Never before, until now, has the tension between science and the human conscience, between technology and ethics, reached a point where it has become a threat to the world as a whole. We are so dazzled that we do not perceive the threats hanging over our heads, warning us of

the pressing need for a radically new and universally ethical outlook.' (UNESCO, May, 1988)

Global Education : Holistic Thinking for Applied Humanism

Global Education emerged as a distinct departure from the bleak culture the world has been offering since few decades. Global Education teaches how young people will live in an increasingly problematic world, how they will live creatively and cooperatively instead of destructively in this Global Village. Global Education is not an additional subject to be taught separately in an already loaded curriculum. It is a special outlook, a dimension that can be implemented in every classroom and in every subject. " It broadens horizons and encourages exploration of all subjects from a global perspective. It contributes to the whole curriculum and enhances our understanding of the world." (Hicks, David, 2003, P.6). Students', global consciousness and empathy with world conditions will help them to acquire a better comprehension of tensions pertaining to economic perspectives, environmental sustainability, gender equality, universal human rights. A transformative paradigm suggests change and change can only begin with the individual. The fundamental aim of the transformative paradigm is to act as an agent which is an inevitable benchmark for Global Education. Hin (1993, P-152) identifies five themes in this respect : (a) ethical living (b) Planetary Survival (c) ecological security (d) think globally-act locally and (e) conscientizing and empowering pedagogy. Global Education is transformative as opposed to merely additive. The knowledge and awareness of self in relation to those around us has been

sprouted from the theory of emotional intelligence that simply denotes: the outer world acts as a mirror to our inner world. The essence of this mutuality is best reflected in the following lines :-

If I am despairing of myself, I despair of the world's future.

If I am hopeful of myself, I have hope for the world.

If I am uncaring of myself, I am careless of my environment.

If I am loving, I see the world as cooperative and caring.

If I am helpless, I see the world at the mercy of events.

Four A's act as essential components of global citizenship where the development of self is tied to the development of social responsibility : attachment, achievement, autonomy and altruism. The three major educational ideologies that are shaping global society are as follows :

- (1) Neo-liberal educational ideology
- (2) Human Rights Education and value judgement
- (3) Environmentalism

The cultural roots of the society influence and render sustainability. Educational principles and practices have to be linked to the cultural anthropology, social psychology and socio-linguistics.

Human rights are results of humanity and human conscience - demand for dignity, respect, justice, protection and freedom, all are needed for a decent human existence.

If the globe itself is destroyed, the earth becomes brittle, we cannot have a global society.

Global Education : An Enquiry Concerning Humane Understanding

In their article, 'Seven Worlds of Moral Education,' Joseph and Efron (March, 2005) review seven practices, each of which has separate dimension of its own, yet all are intrinsically connected with one another.

Character Education :

Every education system must aspire to the good of community. It must promote a new élan in which every individual is in solidarity with the other one. Schooling can and should shape the behavior of young children by inculcating the proper virtues: self-discipline, compassion, empathy perseverance, honesty, friendship and faith within an expanded vision of education.

Cultural Heritage :

Transaction of the curriculum needs to be culture-specific; for example, the teacher while explaining concepts, illustrations and examples needs to draw from indigenous socio-cultural environment. Values emphasized here would include " respect for people and their feelings, and living in harmony with nature".

Caring Community :

This model emphasizes the social and emotional health of all its members: nurturing, proximity, emotional attachment and supportive relationships. Interpersonal and intercultural understanding is accentuated through inclusiveness. Research strongly supports that " students with a strong sense of community are more likely to act ethically and altruistically,

develop social and emotional competencies, avoid violent behaviour, and be academically motivated.

Peace Education :

Peace Education is a profound sense of responsibility for the fate of our planet and for the well-being of humanity with an awareness of the interdependence of all things. It includes conflict resolution, human rights education, multicultural studies, environmental education etc.

Just Community :

This concept has been emerged from the ideas of Kohlberg where moral reasoning follows stages of development. Students are encouraged to reflect their opinions on real-world dilemmas, such as “freedom combined with responsibility, cooperation over competition and how to balance the needs of individuals with those of the community”. This approach “taps students’ idealism for bringing about a better world- to heal, repair, and transform the world”.

Ethical Inquiry :

The education must also promote in each person a vision of permanent change, generate beings that are not simple and passive watchers of their environment. But, on the contrary, every person is the generator of a transformation and development and in consequence, they are capable of questioning, of emitting reasonable judgment, of promoting proposals and inviting to the action to gain the good of community. Ethical inquiry should be integrated into all academic areas for students to appreciate other view points and to bring different perspectives into their own deliberations.

Implications for Teaching and Learning through Curriculum Integration in Global Education.

There are various starting points for infusing a global perspective into existing school curriculum :

- (a) School must be an extended family, a light house and the teachers are exemplars.
- (b) Problems should not be observed in isolation ; they should be analyzed taking all possible relationships among them.
- (c) It is a must to link the present with the future.
- (d) Students are sensitized to the fact that our interrelatedness always implies the question of morality.
- (e) Self-reflection is necessary for open-mindedness and objectivity. Students need to acquire an inclusive and altruistic ethos.
- (f) Global Education must be integrated into existing curriculum using multidisciplinary approach. Students should be involved in at least one project per year (individually, small groups or whole school) where teaching and learning affects positive change.
- (g) In this type of global pedagogy, learning is self-motivated and self-directed. The major focus has been on understanding ‘child as the constructor of knowledge’. Knowledge-building entails a dynamic interaction between teachers, learners and multiple sources of information.

- (h) Learning must be authentic if it is to be meaningful—students must see a connection between the classroom and the ‘real’ world. Students of all ages should be given the opportunity, through curricular content, to become familiar with the external world.
- (i) Becoming good and virtuous is more important than becoming smart and competent.
- (j) We should commit to this global ethic, to understanding one another, to socially-beneficial, peace-fostering, and nature-friendly ways of life.

Conclusion :

We have come to know that Global Education is such an educational dimension that opens our mind’s eye. So, Global Education is multi-dimensional with multiple perspectives; it is critical as well as creative. It awakens to bring about a world of greater justice, equity and human rights for all. It is an extra filter to help children make sense of all the information and opinion the world is throwing at them. Researchers have tried to highlight on the philosophical cum- ethical genesis of Global Education in general and its implementational ethology in particular. But what is most important is to cultivate a global mindset

According to cognitive psychology every mindset stands for a knowledge structure which is constituted by two primary attributes – differentiation, i.e., ability to differ and integration, i.e., ability to synthesize various perspectives. Existing curriculum and methodologies of teaching are able to adapt the

global mindset. Global Education must exert its influence from early childhood education onward and through a broad range of disciplines to build a global education culture. Hence, greater commitment from all sectors and preparation of a sound, realistic plan of action can help us achieve Global education and transform the movement into a mass movement to achieve a better global ethics and peaceful existence. Indeed, this is one of the greatest challenges in the 21st century. Global Education makes another world possible and in this respect we can say without hesitation that it is the Teachers’ initiatives that Matter!

If you think about a song, then all the songs of this world are yours.

If you think about a single flower, then all the flowers of this universe belong to you.

If you think about the light, then the sun is yours.

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